

1 **Short title:** Temperature signalling in guard cells

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5 **Guard cells integrate light and temperature signals to control stomatal aperture**

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15

16 **One-sentence summary:** High temperature-mediated stomatal opening involves
17 crosstalk with light signalling pathways.

18

19 **Author contributions:** AMH, AND and KAF conceived the project and supervised
20 experiments. K-IK, A C-L, VCB, MG, PS, FJM and DHM performed experiments. K-IK,
21 A C-L, VCB, MG, PS, FJM, DPF, AMH, AND and KAF analysed data. K-IK, A C-L and
22 KAF wrote the manuscript with contributions from all authors.

23

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29

30 **Abstract**

31 High temperature promotes guard cell expansion, which opens stomatal pores to facilitate
32 leaf cooling. How the high temperature signal is perceived and transmitted to regulate
33 stomatal aperture is, however, unknown. Here, we used a reverse-genetics approach to
34 understand high temperature-mediated stomatal opening in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. Our
35 findings reveal that high temperature-induced guard cell movement requires components
36 involved in blue light-mediated stomatal opening, suggesting crosstalk between light and
37 temperature signalling pathways. The molecular players involved include phototropin
38 photoreceptors, plasma membrane H⁺-ATPases, and multiple members of the 14-3-3
39 protein family. We further show that phototropin-deficient mutants display impaired
40 rosette evapotranspiration and leaf cooling at high temperatures. Blocking the interaction
41 of 14-3-3 proteins with their client proteins severely impairs high temperature-induced
42 stomatal opening, but has no effect on the induction of heat-sensitive guard cell
43 transcripts, supporting the existence of an additional intracellular high-temperature
44 response pathway in plants.

45

46 **Introduction**

47 Plants experience constant fluctuations in temperature and are increasingly exposed to
48 global heatwaves (Perkins et al. 2012). Despite the importance of temperature for plant
49 growth and development, the molecular mechanisms controlling temperature perception
50 in angiosperms have only recently started to emerge. High temperature-induced
51 hypocotyl elongation has been attributed, in part, to accelerated reversion of the plant

52 photoreceptor phytochrome B (phyB) to its inactive Pr form during long nights and at low
53 light levels (Jung et al., 2016; Legris et al., 2016). PhyB inactivation elevates abundance
54 of the bHLH transcription factor PHYTOCHROME INTERACTING FACTOR 4 (PIF4),
55 driving auxin biosynthesis and stem elongation (Koini et al., 2009; Franklin et al., 2011;
56 Jung et al., 2016). PIF4 additionally promotes the accumulation of *FLOWERING LOCUS*
57 *T (FT)* transcript to accelerate flowering in short photoperiods (Kumar et al., 2012). High
58 temperature-mediated upregulation of *FT* and *HEAT SHOCK PROTEIN 70 (HSP70)*
59 transcripts involves eviction of the alternative histone, H2A.Z, from nucleosomes. Mutants
60 deficient in the ACTIN-RELATED PROTEIN 6 (ARP6) subunit of the SWR1 chromatin
61 remodelling complex are unable to insert H2A.Z into nucleosomes and therefore display
62 a constitutive warm-temperature transcriptome (Kumar and Wigge, 2010). Induction of
63 HSPs by heat shock in Arabidopsis protoplasts has further been shown to involve the
64 heat-activated calcium channel CYCLIC NUCLEOTIDE-GATED ION CHANNEL 6
65 (CNGC6) (Gao et al., 2012).

66

67 Elucidation of plant temperature signalling networks is confounded by the fact that
68 commonly measured physiological outputs of temperature change (stem elongation,
69 flowering time) can be temporally and spatially distant from the temperature perception
70 event, requiring inter-cellular, inter-tissue, and inter-organ signalling networks. To
71 address this constraint, we have used the Arabidopsis guard cell as a single-cell model
72 to study high temperature-regulated physiological and gene expression responses in
73 parallel. Guard cells surround epidermal pores, termed stomata. They can adjust their
74 turgor in response to environmental stimuli to regulate stomatal aperture, thereby

75 controlling gas and water exchange between leaves at the atmosphere (Hetherington and
76 Woodward, 2003). Stomatal opening is promoted by blue light and involves the
77 phototropin photoreceptors and their downstream target BLUE LIGHT SIGNALLING 1
78 (BLUS1) (Kinoshita et al. 2001; Takemiya et al., 2013). When grown in well-watered
79 conditions at elevated temperature (28°C), Arabidopsis plants display increased
80 transpiration and architectural adaptations to enhance evaporative cooling (Crawford et
81 al., 2012; Bridge et al., 2013). Greater stomatal conductance has been observed in
82 multiple species exposed to temperatures up to 40°C, although interpreting the effects of
83 temperature on stomatal function *in planta* is confounded by the effects of temperature
84 on vapour pressure deficit and photosynthesis (Urban et al., 2017). Stomatal aperture
85 can be quantified in isolated epidermises via stomatal bioassays. This approach provides
86 a single-cell system that offers unique advantages for studying thermosensory signalling;
87 cells heat up uniformly and complications arising from the interplay between increased
88 temperature and humidity are removed. Epidermal strip bioassays have shown that
89 temperatures between 30°C and 45°C drive stomatal opening in faba bean (*Vicia faba*;
90 Rogers et al., 1979; Rogers et al., 1980). Further analyses in protoplasts have shown that
91 elevated temperature (36°C) increases the currents through hyperpolarization-activated
92 K⁺ channels in guard-cell membranes (Ilan et al., 1995). Molecular understanding of this
93 process is limited but stomatal opening in response to heat stress (38°C) has been shown
94 to involve the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) by RESPIRATORY BURST
95 OXIDASE PROTEIN D (RBOHD) in Arabidopsis (Devireddy et al. 2019). Furthermore, FT
96 has been reported to promote stomatal opening (Kinoshita et al., 2011), providing a link
97 between high temperature and stomatal aperture.

98

99 In this study, we report the existence of a high-temperature signalling pathway controlling
100 Arabidopsis guard cell movement that requires phototropins and plasma membrane (PM)
101 H⁺-ATPase activity for full stomatal opening, yet operates independently from known high
102 temperature-signalling components. Perturbation of this pathway disrupts stomatal
103 opening but not heat-induced transcript accumulation, suggesting either the existence of
104 multiple thermosensing mechanisms or bifurcation of a thermosensory pathway upstream
105 of PM H⁺-ATPase activation.

106

107 **Results**

108 **Isolated guard cells respond to high temperature in the light and the dark**

109 Stomatal responses to high temperature were investigated using epidermal peel
110 bioassays to ensure that temperature effects could be analysed in isolation, without
111 confounding alterations in humidity. High temperature-induced stomatal opening was
112 clearly visible in isolated epidermal tissue containing viable guard cells (Figure 1A). As
113 the epidermis can no longer receive signals from the mesophyll layer and adjacent
114 pavement cells are ruptured, guard cells must possess the necessary molecular
115 machinery to perceive temperature changes. High temperature-mediated stomatal
116 opening occurred in the light and the dark, with 35°C in the light resulting in the greatest
117 response (Figure 1B). High temperature-induced stomatal opening was observed in
118 isolated barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) and *Commelina communis* epidermises at 40°C
119 (Supplemental Figure 1), suggesting conservation of this pathway in angiosperms. In
120 Arabidopsis, 35°C treatment had no effect on guard cell viability, as identified by staining

121 with fluorescein diacetate (Supplemental Figure 2A-2G). Shifting peels from 35°C to 22°C
122 led to statistically significant stomatal closure in the light and the dark, confirming that the
123 response is reversible (Supplemental Figure 2H). The rapidity of the response was
124 demonstrated in time-course analyses, whereby significant stomatal opening was
125 observed within 45 min (Figure 1C).

126

127 **High temperature-mediated stomatal opening in isolated guard cells requires** 128 **phototropins and plasma membrane H⁺-ATPase activity**

129 The involvement of known high-temperature signalling components in high temperature-
130 mediated stomatal opening was investigated via stomatal bioassays using the *cngc*, *arp6*,
131 *pif4*, and *ft* null mutants (Figure 2A-C). We considered phyB to be an unlikely candidate
132 for multiple reasons. PhyB is a weak positive regulator of stomatal opening (Wang et al.,
133 2010), so inactivation of phyB at warm temperatures would promote stomatal closure
134 rather than opening (Jung et al., 2016). Thermal reversion of phyB is additionally mostly
135 effective in the dark and at low-light levels (Jung et al., 2016; Legris et al., 2016), whereas
136 the opening of Arabidopsis stomata by 35°C treatment is maximally effective at high-light
137 levels. All of the mutants tested had wild-type (WT) apertures at 35°C, suggesting that
138 high temperature-mediated stomatal opening does not involve these known
139 thermosensory mechanisms. Mutants deficient in FT displayed reduced stomatal
140 apertures following transfer from the dark to (red + blue) light, consistent with previous
141 studies (Supplemental Figure 3; Kinoshita *et al.*, 2011), but showed WT stomatal
142 apertures when maintained in white light. The reported thermosensory activity of
143 phototropin photoreceptors (Fujii et al., 2017) led us to additionally investigate the role of

144 phototropins and their downstream target, BLUS1, in high temperature-mediated
145 stomatal opening. Loss of phototropins and BLUS1 resulted in significantly reduced
146 stomatal apertures at 22°C (Figure 2D). This is consistent with the established roles of
147 these proteins in blue-light signalling (Kinoshita et al. 2001; Takemiya et al., 2013).
148 Impaired stomatal opening was most severe in the *phot1/2* mutant (Figure 2D), confirming
149 the redundant action of these photoreceptors (Kinoshita et al., 2001) and suggesting the
150 existence of a phototropin-mediated, BLUS1-independent pathway controlling stomatal
151 opening in plants maintained in white light. All blue light-signalling mutants displayed a
152 stomatal opening response to high temperature, but this was strongly impaired in
153 *phot1/phot2* mutants, where a significant interaction between genotype and temperature
154 was recorded (Figure 2D). These data suggest that a small amount of guard cell
155 movement can occur in response to 35°C independently of phototropin, but complete
156 stomatal opening requires phototropin activation. *blus1-3* mutants displayed significantly
157 smaller stomatal apertures than WT plants at 35°C, suggesting a partial involvement in
158 this response.

159

160 Influx of K⁺ and water into guard cells increases turgor, increasing stomatal aperture
161 (Outlaw and Lowry, 1977; Kwak et al., 2001). A role for inward K⁺ channels in guard cell
162 responses to high temperature has been reported (Ilan et al., 1995), so we decided to
163 investigate potential upstream regulators. A requirement for the activation of inward K⁺
164 channels is the hyperpolarization of the PM through the activation of the PM H⁺-ATPase
165 (Assmann et al., 1985; Kinoshita and Shimazaki, 1999; Roelfsema et al., 2001).
166 Treatment of epidermal peels with the ATPase and phosphatase inhibitor sodium

167 orthovanadate (Ueno et al., 2005; Kinoshita et al., 2011) resulted in reduced stomatal
168 apertures at 35°C, suggesting a possible role for the PM H⁺-ATPase downstream of high-
169 temperature perception (Figure 3A), although the broad-spectrum activity of this
170 compound required supporting data from reverse-genetics studies to substantiate this
171 conclusion. There are 11 functional members of the PM H⁺-ATPase family in Arabidopsis
172 (AHA1-11), all of which are expressed in guard cells (Ueno et al., 2005). *AHA1*, *AHA2*,
173 and *AHA5* show the highest transcript accumulation in guard-cell protoplasts (Ueno et al.,
174 2005) and thus were selected for further analysis. Impairment in stomatal opening was
175 detected in *aha1-8* under both temperature regimes, suggesting that *AHA1* mediates
176 light-induced guard cell movement and *AHA1* function is required for complete stomatal
177 opening under high temperatures (Figure 3B). The *aha1-6* allele displayed a similar
178 phenotype to *aha1-8* (Supplemental Figure 4). By contrast, the two mutant alleles of *aha2*
179 (*aha 2-5* and *aha 2-4*) displayed reduced stomatal apertures at 35°C but not at 22°C
180 (Figure 3B, Supplemental Figure 4). Together, these data suggest a specific role for
181 *AHA2* in high temperature-mediated stomatal opening. WT stomatal opening phenotypes
182 were observed in the *aha5* mutant at both temperatures (Figure 3B). The *aha1aha2*
183 double mutant is embryonic lethal and thus it could not be investigated (Haruta et al.,
184 2010). *PROTON ATPASE TRANSLOCATION CONTROL 1 (PATROL1)* encodes a
185 translocator protein that moves AHAs in and out of the PM, and was found to be essential
186 for stomatal opening in all conditions (Figure 3C; Hashimoto-Sugimoto et al., 2013).
187
188 *PROTON PUMP INTERACTOR1 (PPI1)* activates *AHA1* (Morandini et al., 2002). We
189 investigated high temperature-mediated stomatal opening in *ppi1* and *ppi2* mutants and

190 detected only a mild stomatal opening defect for *ppi1* at 22°C, consistent with a role for
191 PPI1 in activating AHA1 in response to light (Figure 3C; Morandini et al., 2002; Anzi et
192 al., 2008).

193

194 **14-3-3 proteins mediate stomatal opening in isolated guard cells in response to** 195 **high temperature**

196 One of the best-characterised mechanisms for the activation of the PM H⁺-ATPase
197 involves interaction with a 14-3-3 protein. There are 13 members of the 14-3-3 protein
198 family in Arabidopsis (Sehnke et al., 2002), all of which are expressed in guard cells
199 according to the Arabidopsis eFP browser (Winter et al., 2007). We used 14-3-3 single
200 mutants to systematically investigate whether these regulators participated in a high
201 temperature-specific stomatal opening pathway. Five mutants (*pi*, *phi*, *chi*, *omega*, and
202 *psi*) displayed significantly reduced stomatal apertures at 35°C, but not at 22°C, when
203 compared to WT controls (Figure 4A, B). These observations suggest that multiple
204 members, particularly of the non-epsilon clade, share a role in high temperature-mediated
205 guard cell movement. 14-3-3 *epsilon* was not included in this analysis because we were
206 unable to generate a homozygous line. To further establish the importance of 14-3-3
207 proteins in high temperature-induced stomatal opening, we incubated WT epidermal
208 peels with 5-aminoimidazole-4-carboxamide-1-β-D-ribofuranoside (AICAR), which is a 5'-
209 AMP-mimetic successfully used in plants to inhibit the interaction of 14-3-3s with their
210 client proteins (Toroser et al., 1998; Camoni et al., 2000; Paul et al., 2005; Lozano-Durán
211 et al., 2014). This treatment blocked high temperature-mediated stomatal opening by
212 approximately 70% (Figure 4C). Higher order mutants showed reduced stomatal

213 apertures at 22°C in some combinations (*klpc* and *unpc*), but did not reveal any additive
214 phenotypes at high temperature, suggesting the existence of complex interactions
215 between 14-3-3 proteins (Figure 4D).

216

217 **Calcium influx does not drive high temperature-mediated stomatal opening in** 218 **isolated guard cells**

219 Calcium channels have an established role in heat sensing and thermotolerance in land
220 plants (Saidi et al., 2009; Finka et al., 2012). Movement of calcium from the apoplast,
221 however, promotes stomatal closure (De Silva et al., 1985). To establish whether high
222 temperature responses of guard cells involve Ca^{2+} signalling, epidermal peels were
223 incubated with increasing calcium concentrations. Addition of 50 μM CaCl_2 to the
224 incubation buffer was sufficient to impair high temperature-induced stomatal opening,
225 whereas treatment with 100 μM CaCl_2 at 35°C resulted in the same absolute aperture
226 values as untreated stomata at 22°C (Figure 5A). Incubation of peels with chelating
227 agents 1,2-bis(2-aminophenoxy)ethane-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid (BAPTA) and ethylene
228 glycol tetraacetic acid (EGTA) hindered the inhibition of stomatal opening by added
229 extracellular calcium and allowed for much greater apertures to be achieved at 35°C than
230 in the absence of BAPTA or EGTA (Figure 5B,C). Stomata subjected to added CaCl_2 did
231 not, however, open as expected in response to high temperature in the solvent control
232 condition (Figure 5B). We attribute this to the presence of DMSO (0.4% v/v), which can
233 induce the formation of water pores on the PM (Notman et al., 2006), thus increasing
234 dramatically the uptake of calcium. We further observed that calcium import leading to
235 stomatal closure occurred through verapamil-insensitive channels at both temperatures

236 (Figure 5D). Collectively, the application of chelating agents and calcium-channel
237 blockers showed that influx of external calcium reduces stomatal aperture and therefore
238 can be excluded as a high-temperature signal driving opening. In line with this conclusion,
239 analyses of the inward-rectifying calcium channel mutants *cngc6* and *reduced*
240 *hyperosmolality-induced [Ca²⁺]_i increase 1 (osca1-4)* revealed no impairment of high
241 temperature-mediated guard cell movement (Figure 2A, Figure 5E). Conversely,
242 treatment with the membrane-permeable form of the calcium chelator BAPTA (BAPTA-
243 AM) (Young et al., 2006) inhibited high temperature-induced stomatal opening,
244 suggesting a possible signalling role for intracellular calcium (Figure 5F). The vacuolar-
245 membrane two pore calcium channel mutant *two pore calcium channel 1 (tpc1-2)* retained
246 WT stomatal apertures in response to high temperature, showing that TPC1 is not
247 required for the response (Figure 5E).

248

249 **Phototropins promote evapotranspiration and leaf cooling at high temperature**

250 The involvement of phototropins and AHA2 in high temperature-mediated stomatal
251 opening was further explored *in planta*, through gravimetric measurements of
252 transpiration and thermal imaging. WT, *aha2-5*, and *phot1/phot2* rosettes were grown in
253 a similar manner to plants used for epidermal strip bioassays for 4.5 weeks. Consistent
254 with previous reports (Sakamoto and Briggs, 2002), *phot1/phot2* mutants displayed
255 severe leaf curling (Supplemental Figure 5), which results in altered boundary layer
256 conductance. We measured whole-plant transpiration, whole-plant temperature, and
257 calculated rosette conductance as $E/VPD_{\text{leaf-air}}$. On day 1 of the experiment,
258 measurements were recorded at a constant temperature of 22°C. In contrast to *aha2-5*

259 mutants that resembled WT controls, *phot1/phot2* plants displayed elevated rosette
260 temperature (Figure 6A, B) and lower rosette conductance (Figure 6C, D). On day 2, the
261 same protocol was repeated for 3 h post-dawn to enable transpiration to stabilise. Half
262 the plants were then transferred to identical light conditions at 33°C. This was the
263 maximum temperature that could be used without generating a large change in vapour
264 pressure deficit (VPD_{air}) between 22°C and high-temperature treatment. Transfer to 33°C
265 resulted in a rapid increase in rosette temperature, which was maintained at ca. 29°C in
266 WT and *aha2-5* plants (Figure 7A, B). This elevation was accompanied by a large
267 increase in rosette conductance (Figure 7C, D). In *phot1/phot2* plants, rosette
268 temperature reached higher values and the increase in rosette conductance was reduced
269 when compared to WT controls (Figure 7). No differences in stomatal density or index
270 were recorded in *aha5-2* or *phot1/phot2* mutants (Supplemental Figure 6), suggesting
271 that phototropins contribute to high temperature-mediated stomatal opening *in planta*.

272

273 **Stomatal opening and transcriptional responses to high temperature are not**
274 **mediated by a linear thermosensing pathway in guard cells**

275 To explore signalling crosstalk between different high-temperature responses, we
276 analysed the transcript abundance of high temperature-induced marker genes in isolated
277 guard cells treated with AICAR. We hypothesised that if high temperature-mediated
278 stomatal opening and transcription were controlled by a linear thermosensory pathway,
279 then perturbation of this signalling cascade would impair both responses. The abundance
280 of two high temperature-induced transcripts, namely *HEAT SHOCK PROTEIN 70*
281 (*HSP70*) and *HEAT SHOCK PROTEIN 18.2* (*HSP18.2*), were measured in epidermal

282 peels at 22°C and 35°C in the presence or absence of AICAR, a pharmacological inhibitor
283 of the 14-3-3-PM-H⁺-ATPase interaction and of high temperature-induced stomatal
284 opening (Figure 8A). Consistent with previous reports, the guard cell-specific transcripts
285 *GC1* and *MYB60* (Yang et al. 2008) displayed higher relative transcript abundances in
286 epidermal peels than in corresponding leaf tissue, demonstrating that the method used
287 for RNA extraction resulted in guard cell-enriched samples (Supplemental Figure 7A).
288 Quantification of relative transcript abundance with two separate control genes showed
289 that *HSP70* and *HSP18.2* transcripts accumulated in response to high temperature, even
290 in the presence of AICAR (Figure 8A, Supplemental Figure 7B). Leaf-disk transcript
291 abundances displayed the same trends as the guard cell-enriched samples
292 (Supplemental Figures 7C-D). *HSP70* promoter activity was additionally recorded using
293 transgenic lines expressing the *HSP70::LUCIFERASE* reporter (Kumar and Wigge,
294 2010). The *HSP70* promoter had similar high-temperature responses in the presence or
295 absence of AICAR, consistent with the transcript data (Figure 8B).

296

297 **Discussion**

298 When atmospheric relative humidity is not a restrictive factor, plants respond to high
299 temperature by opening their stomata. This physiological response occurs under
300 laboratory and field conditions in a number of species (Willmer and Mansfield, 1970;
301 Rogers et al., 1979; Rogers et al., 1980; Sadras et al., 2012; Mendes and Marengo, 2017;
302 Urban et al., 2017). Despite the conservation of this response, little is known about how
303 guard cells perceive and transduce temperature signals. Here we show that high
304 temperatures induce stomatal opening in *Arabidopsis*, barley, and *Commelina communis*

305 (Figure 1, Supplemental Figure 1). We have further characterised the temperature range
306 and kinetics of the Arabidopsis response (Figure 1B, 1C). Incubation of epidermal peels
307 at 35°C led to a statistically significant increase in stomatal aperture without affecting
308 tissue viability and was therefore chosen as the most appropriate treatment to study high-
309 temperature signalling in isolated guard cells (Figure 2B, Supplemental Figure 2).

310

311 Mutants deficient in known thermosensory signalling components (*cngc6*, *arp6*, *ft*)
312 displayed WT apertures at 35°C, suggesting that these components are not required for
313 high temperature-mediated stomatal opening (Figure 2A). Intriguingly, and in contrast to
314 studies using dark to (red + blue) light transfer, *ft* mutants maintained in white light
315 displayed WT stomatal apertures at 22°C (Figure 2C, Supplemental Figure 3). It is
316 therefore possible that FT functions predominantly to promote stomatal opening following
317 a dark to light transfer. In this study, plants were grown in 10-h photoperiods. A striking
318 reduction in *FT* transcript abundance has been recorded in guard-cell protoplasts isolated
319 from plants grown in short photoperiods compared to protoplasts extracted from plants
320 grown in long photoperiods (Aoki et al., 2019). The similar stomatal apertures observed
321 in WT and *ft* mutants under white light in this study might, therefore, be due to low *FT*
322 levels in WT guard cells. Increased ambient temperature elevates auxin biosynthesis in
323 Arabidopsis seedlings via a process mediated by PIF4 (Franklin et al. 2011). Auxins have
324 been shown to promote stomatal opening by limiting hydrogen peroxide production in
325 guard cells (Dodd, 2003; Song et al., 2006). Mutants deficient in PIF4 displayed WT
326 stomatal opening responses to elevated temperature, suggesting that auxin elevation is
327 not a key regulatory mechanism underlying this response (Figure 2A).

328

329 A thermosensory role for the phototropin blue light photoreceptors has been suggested
330 following observations that the lifetime of photoactivated phototropin is temperature-
331 dependent in multiple species (Kodama et al., 2008; Nakasone et al., 2008; Fujii et al.,
332 2017). Phototropins contain two light, oxygen, or voltage (LOV) domains at their
333 photosensory N-terminal domain that bind flavin mononucleotide (FMN) chromophores.
334 In *Marchantia polymorpha*, the single MpPHOT photoreceptor has been shown to
335 regulate cold-induced chloroplast movement, with low temperature prolonging the
336 lifespan of the active LOV2 domain. Warmer temperatures cause the reversion of LOV2
337 to an inactive state, preventing the response (Fujii et al., 2017). As phototropins promote
338 blue light-induced stomatal opening (Kinoshita et al., 2001), we hypothesised that they
339 might function as thermosensors driving high temperature-mediated guard cell
340 movement. Although a small, phototropin-independent response to high temperature was
341 observed, complete stomatal opening required both phot1 and phot2 (Figure 2D). This
342 result was further supported by *in planta* data showing reduced evapotranspiration and
343 leaf cooling in high temperature-treated *phot1/phot2* mutants (Figures 6,7). As warm
344 temperatures have been shown to inactivate phototropin signalling in *Marchantia* spp.
345 (Fujii et al., 2017), it is unclear how exposure to high temperature would lead to enhanced
346 phototropin activity. The situation in *Arabidopsis* is, however, more complex with the
347 lifespan of LOV2 altered through interactions with other phototropin domains (Kasahara
348 et al. 2002). Alternatively, high temperature may regulate signalling pathways
349 downstream of phototropin, rather than the activity of the photoreceptor itself (Figure 9).
350 The existence of an additional phototropin-independent pathway may explain why some

351 high temperature-mediated stomatal opening can also be observed in the dark (Figure
352 1B). It is possible that this response is mediated by RBOHD-mediated ROS production
353 (Devireddy et al. 2019).

354

355 Blue light activates the PM H⁺-ATPase, causing PM hyperpolarisation that in turn
356 activates inward-rectifying K⁺ channels and stomatal opening (Shimazaki et al., 1986;
357 Schroeder et al., 1987; Kinoshita and Shimazaki, 1999; Ueno et al., 2005). In faba bean,
358 high temperature regulates the activity of inward and outward rectifying K⁺ channels
359 consistent with the induction of stomatal opening (Ilan et al., 1995). Here, we provide
360 genetic evidence suggesting that AHA1 and AHA2 are required for a full stomatal opening
361 response to high temperature in epidermal peels. An additional role for AHA1 in light-
362 induced stomatal opening was also observed (Figure 3B, Supplemental Figure 4).
363 Consistent with our findings, AHA1 was recently reported to play a major role in blue light-
364 induced stomatal opening, whereas *aha2* and *aha5* mutants showed no impairment of
365 the response (Yamauchi et al., 2016). In addition to the C-terminal autoinhibitory domain,
366 PM H⁺-ATPase pump activity is controlled by N-terminal domain variations, which may
367 provide a mechanism for posttranslational regulation by different factors (Ekberg et al.,
368 2010). Recruitment of AHA1, and possibly other AHA isoforms, to the PM in guard cells
369 is mediated by the Munc13-like protein PATROL1 (Hashimoto-Sugimoto et al., 2013). We
370 provide evidence that *PATROL1* is essential for stomatal opening in response to high
371 temperature, as is the case for fusicoccin, low CO₂, and blue light (Figure 3C; Hashimoto-
372 Sugimoto et al., 2013).

373

374 To address how AHAs become activated in the high-temperature pathway, we
375 investigated potential roles for AHA-regulating 14-3-3 proteins and the AHA-interacting
376 proteins PPI. In response to blue light, 14-3-3 proteins, acting as dimers, bind to the
377 autoinhibitory C-terminal region of the PM H⁺-ATPase and promote pumping (Jahn et al.,
378 1997; Oecking et al., 1997; Wu et al., 1997; Emi et al., 2001). Genetic analyses of single
379 and higher order 14-3-3 mutants revealed that they collectively contribute to high
380 temperature-mediated stomatal opening with potentially antagonistic interactions
381 between isoforms (Figure 4). Isoform-specific redundancy and antagonism between 14-
382 3-3 proteins has previously been reported in Arabidopsis root growth (Van Kleeff et al.,
383 2014). Of the fourteen members present in Arabidopsis, 14-3-3 PHI and LAMBDA have
384 been shown to be important for blue light-induced stomatal opening (Kinoshita and
385 Shimazaki, 1999; Ueno et al., 2005; Tseng et al., 2012). 14-3-3 isoforms of the non-
386 epsilon group are more effective at activating the proton pump when compared to the
387 epsilon group, a result which mirrors our data (Figure 4; Pallucca et al., 2014). The C-
388 and N-termini of each 14-3-3 isoform are highly specific and members of the family
389 demonstrate variation in binding affinity to the proton pump AHA2 (Rosenquist et al.,
390 2000; Alsterfjord et al., 2004). Different family members may therefore activate the proton
391 pump in response to environmental stimuli. Furthermore, 14-3-3 proteins can homo- and
392 heterodimerize. Their subcellular localisation depends on cell type and may be driven by
393 client interactions, presenting multiple input points for environmental factors to exert their
394 influence (Oecking et al., 1997; Wu et al., 1997; Paul et al., 2005; Chang et al., 2009).
395

396 Treatment with AICAR severely impaired high temperature-induced stomatal opening,
397 highlighting the importance of 14-3-3 interactions in this response (Figure 3A). It is
398 interesting to note that AICAR treatment has also been shown to suppress PAMP-
399 triggered stomatal closure (Lozano-Durán et al., 2014), suggesting that the function of
400 14-3-3s is context-dependent. 14-3-3 proteins have several clients in addition to the PM
401 H⁺-ATPase and it is possible that AICAR effects on high temperature-mediated stomatal
402 opening may be related to other channels (Gobert et al., 2007; Latz et al., 2007;
403 Sottocornola et al., 2006; Ichida et al., 1997). Further analysis is required to determine
404 whether interaction of AHA2 with 14-3-3 proteins is enhanced at high temperature (Figure
405 9). Despite clear evidence suggesting a role for AHA2 in high temperature-mediated
406 stomatal opening in epidermal peels, *aha2-5* mutants displayed WT levels of rosette
407 conductance and leaf cooling at high temperature (Figure 7). This discrepancy may result
408 from the reduced sensitivity of *in planta* assays and redundancy between family members
409 (e.g. AHA1) and/or the masking of AHA2 signalling in leaves resulting from signals from
410 neighbouring cells.

411

412 External calcium antagonises high temperature-induced stomatal opening (Figure 5A),
413 which may result from the reversible inhibition of PM H⁺-ATPase activity (Kinoshita et al.,
414 1995). Pharmacological evidence has suggested a role for intracellular calcium stores in
415 blue light-induced stomatal opening (Shimazaki et al., 1992). In addition, low CO₂
416 produces more [Ca²⁺]_{cyt} transients compared to elevated CO₂ and also increases stomatal
417 apertures (Young et al., 2006). Both stomatal movements in response to CO₂ and [Ca²⁺]_{cyt}
418 transients were inhibited by BAPTA-AM treatment (Young et al., 2006). In our study,

419 BAPTA-AM treatment reduced high temperature-mediated stomatal opening, supporting
420 a role for intracellular calcium (Figure 5D), although the existence and source of $[Ca^{2+}]_{cyt}$
421 transients at high temperature remain to be identified. Increased calcium concentration in
422 the micromolar region promotes the association of 14-3-3 proteins with PM H⁺-ATPases
423 (Manak and Ferl, 2007). Conversely, millimolar concentrations of calcium inhibit the
424 dimerization of the 14-3-3 protein family member PSI and its interaction with client
425 proteins (Abarca et al., 1999). It is therefore possible that local changes in calcium
426 concentration may regulate the function of 14-3-3 proteins during high temperature-
427 induced stomatal opening.

428

429 Although AICAR inhibited high temperature-induced guard cell movement, it did not affect
430 the accumulation of heat-responsive transcripts (Figure 8, Supplemental Figure 7). This
431 is in agreement with a study demonstrating that PECTIN METHYLESTERASE34
432 (PME34) is required for acquired thermotolerance and stomatal movements, but is not
433 required for the induction of heat-shock genes or accumulation of heat-shock proteins
434 (Huang et al., 2017). *CNGC6* facilitates the expression of heat-shock proteins during
435 acquired thermotolerance (Gao et al., 2012), but loss of this channel protein does not
436 impair high temperature-induced stomatal opening (Figure 2A). Furthermore, chromatin
437 remodelling mediated by ARP6 is involved in high temperature-mediated transcription,
438 yet *arp6* mutant stomata opened fully in response to high temperature (Figure 2A; Kumar
439 and Wigge, 2010). These data suggest either the existence of discrete thermosensing
440 mechanisms in different cellular compartments of guard cells, or the divergence of a
441 single thermosensory pathway upstream of 14-3-3-PM H⁺-ATPase interaction.

442

443 In conclusion, we demonstrate that Arabidopsis guard cells integrate light and
444 temperature information to control stomatal aperture. The point at which these signals
445 converge has yet to be elucidated but may involve direct stimulation of phototropin,
446 amplification of phototropin signalling, and/or enhancement of AHA activity, possibly
447 through enhanced 14-3-3 binding (Figure 9). This study also establishes the Arabidopsis
448 guard cell as a tractable system for studying intracellular thermosensing in angiosperms.
449 Future work in this area is essential to facilitate crop production and biodiversity
450 management in a warming climate.

451

452 **Materials and Methods**

453

454 **Plant Material and Growth Conditions**

455 Plant material is described in Supplemental Table 1. SALK and SAIL lines were obtained
456 from the Nottingham Arabidopsis Stock Centre (NASC) and were tested for homozygosity
457 with genomic DNA PCR. For previously uncharacterised lines, exact insertion points were
458 determined by sequencing and transcript levels quantified by RT-qPCR. Seeds were
459 sterilised with chlorine gas according to the protocol of Linsey et al. (2017) and
460 germinated on 1/2 Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium plates (0.22% (w/v) MS salts, 1%
461 (w/v) sucrose, 0.6% agar (w/v), pH 5.8). Seedlings were transplanted to a 3:1 mixture of
462 compost (All purpose growing medium, Sinclair, Ellesmere Port, UK) and sand
463 (Horticultural silver sand, Melcourt, Tetbury, UK), and were grown under a 10-h
464 photoperiod in controlled environment chambers (microclima, Snijders, Tilburg, The

465 Netherlands) irradiated by fluorescent tubes at $150 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. Chambers were set to
466 22°C during the day, 20°C during the night, and 70% relative humidity.

467

468 **Genotyping**

469 To verify the genotype of T-DNA mutants, a 10-mm diameter leaf disk was flash frozen in
470 liquid nitrogen and homogenized with 5-mm stainless steel beads using a TissueLyser II
471 (Qiagen). Ground samples were resuspended with 400 μl extraction buffer (200 mM Tris
472 Cl pH 7.5, 250 mM NaCl, 25 mM EDTA, 0.5% (w/v) SDS), centrifuged at 15000 g for 1
473 min, and the supernatant was transferred to a new tube. An equal volume of ice-cold
474 isopropanol was added and DNA was left to precipitate on ice for 30 min. Samples were
475 centrifuged at 15000 g for 7 min and the pellet was resuspended in 100 μl deionised
476 water. 1 μl of isolate was used as the template in a 25- μl PCR reaction with DreamTaq
477 polymerase (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts). PCR products were
478 analysed by electrophoresis on a 1% (w/v) agarose gel. In the case of previously
479 uncharacterised insertions, PCR products using the T-DNA primer were isolated using
480 the Wizard SV Gel and PCR Clean-Up System (Promega, Madison, Wisconsin) and
481 sequenced. Primer sequences used for genotyping are provided in Supplemental Tables
482 2A and 2B.

483

484

485 **Epidermal Peel Bioassays**

486 4.5 to 6-week-old plants were used for epidermal bioassays. Abaxial epidermal peels
487 were isolated from fully expanded rosette leaves. An incision was performed near the leaf

488 base, between the leaf edge and the midvein. Tissue was pulled from the incision site
489 towards the leaf tip. Peels were trimmed with Vannas scissors to produce segments from
490 the middle of the lamina blade. To prevent stomatal opening during sample preparation,
491 peels were kept in 10/0 buffer (10 mM MES, pH 6.15). Unless specified, peels from 3
492 leaves per genotype, per condition, derived from different plants, were removed and
493 incubated in 10/50 buffer (10 mM MES, 50 mM KCl, pH 6.15) at 22°C for 2 h, illuminated
494 with white light ($100 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) or kept in the dark. These were then transferred to fresh
495 10/50 buffer pre-warmed to the desired temperature and incubated for a further 2 h,
496 unless different time points are specified, under the same light regime. For analyses of *ft*
497 mutant responses to blue light, peels from dark-adapted plants were either maintained in
498 the dark ($\pm 10 \mu\text{M}$ fusicoccin) or transferred at dawn to a mixture of blue light (λ_{max} 470
499 nm, $10 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) + red light (λ_{max} 660 nm, $50 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) provided by LEDs.
500 Following treatments, peels were transferred to microscope slides and immediately
501 covered with a cover slip before imaging. Unless otherwise specified, apertures for 10
502 stomata per peel were measured with an Olympus BX50 microscope attached to a
503 Moticam 580 camera (Motic, Barcelona, Spain). No more than 3 neighbouring stomata
504 and no stomata near the edge of peels were measured. Each experiment was performed
505 independently three times and data presented are the pooled values. Chemical stock
506 solutions used for pharmacological treatments during bioassays were made up with either
507 10/50 buffer [100 mM AICAR (Santa Cruz Biotechnology Inc, Dallas, Texas), 1 M CaCl_2 ,
508 20 mM verapamil hydrochloride (Santa Cruz Biotechnology Inc)]; water [250 mM EGTA
509 (pH adjusted to 8.0 with KOH), 10 mM sodium orthovanadate (pH adjusted to 10 with
510 HCl)]; ethanol [10 μM Fusicoccin (Santa Cruz Biotechnology Inc)]; or DMSO [62.5 mM

511 BAPTA (Santa Cruz Biotechnology Inc), 25 mM BAPTA-AM (Santa Cruz Biotechnology
512 Inc)]. Chemicals made up with water, ethanol, or DMSO were diluted with 10/50 buffer to
513 the final working concentrations. Chemical treatments were added to the fresh 10/50
514 buffer used during the second incubation with the exception of BAPTA-AM, which
515 included an additional loading step as described previously (Young et al., 2006).

516

517 **Viability Staining**

518 To evaluate guard cell viability, epidermal peels were stained with fluorescein diacetate
519 (FDA) immediately after temperature incubations. Peels were transferred to fresh 10/50
520 buffer containing 0.001 (w/v) FDA (Santa Cruz Biotechnology Inc, 1% w/v stock solution
521 in acetone), and incubated at room temperature for 10 min. Peels were briefly washed
522 with 10/50 buffer to remove excess dye and fluorescence was imaged using a Zeiss
523 Axiovert 200M microscope equipped with XBO 75 fluorescent lamp and a GFP filter.
524 Volocity software (Perkin Elmer, Waltham, Massachusetts) was used to analyse the
525 images.

526

527 **Gravimetric analysis of transpiration and thermal imaging**

528 In all experiments, plants were maintained at $150 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. From germination to the
529 end of the experiment, each pot was weighed daily and watered at a target weight to
530 maintain soil water content at $0.65 \text{ g H}_2\text{O g}^{-1}$ dry soil, previously determined as a well-
531 watered level non-limiting for growth and corresponding to 80% of field capacity (as in
532 Rymaszewski et al., 2018). Gravimetric transpiration measurements were undertaken 4.5
533 weeks after sowing, during two consecutive days on seven plants per genotype. Pots

534 were sealed with a double layer of parafilm to prevent water evaporation from the soil. On
535 day 1, all plants were maintained at 22°C and relative humidity at 65%, resulting in a
536 constant VPD_{air} of ca. 0.93 kPa. Each pot was weighed with 10^{-3} g accuracy (Precisa
537 balances XB, Precisa) every hour, starting 1.5 h before light onset. Weight losses
538 between each measurement were used to calculate transpiration rate on a leaf area basis
539 (E), using the total rosette area on the same day for each plant. Each weight
540 measurement was coupled to an individual thermal-infrared image of each plant, taken
541 from above (FLIR E60 Thermal Imaging Camera, FLIR Systems). Reflected temperature
542 was measured with a multidirectional mirror and processed using Thermimage R
543 (Tattersall, 2019). Plant pixels were separated from the image background using
544 temperature thresholds, and the plant temperature was calculated as the average
545 temperature of plant pixels. On day 2, the same plants were measured following the same
546 protocol (hourly weighing and thermal imaging) in the same conditions, starting 1.5 h
547 before light onset. Three hours after light onset, when transpiration was stabilized, plants
548 were transferred to a second cabinet adjusted to 33°C and 75% relative humidity, yielding
549 a VPD_{air} of ca. 1.2 kPa (as close as possible to the VPD_{air} in the control cabinet). Hourly
550 weighing and thermal imaging were then performed for a further 6 h. Measurements of
551 air temperature, air relative humidity, and leaf temperature were used to calculate the leaf
552 to air vapour pressure deficit ($VPD_{leaf-air}$). $E/VPD_{leaf-air}$ was then calculated for each plant
553 at each time point as an estimate of total rosette conductance according to the diffusion
554 equation of water vapour in the air.

555

556 **Determination of rosette area.**

557 Daily estimates of projected rosette area were calculated for each plant using images
558 taken from above every two days and analysed with Ilastik software, version 1.21.7
559 (Sommer et al. 2011). Total pixels corresponding to plants were extracted from
560 background using a random forest classification method based on colour and texture and
561 later converted to mm. Total rosette area was measured 4.5 weeks after sowing by
562 dissecting the plants and was compared to projected rosette area on the same day to
563 determine genotype-dependent coefficients for the ratio of total vs projected rosette area.

564

565 **Stomatal density**

566 Plants were grown in the control conditions described above for transpiration analyses.
567 Five weeks after sowing, impressions of the abaxial surface of two mature rosette leaves
568 from 7 plants per genotype were made with dental resin (President Jet Light Body,
569 Coltène/Whaledent, Burgess Hill, UK). Clear nail varnish was applied to the set
570 impression after removal from the leaf. The varnish impressions were viewed on an
571 Olympus BX51 inverted microscope, fitted with an Olympus DP70 camera, and analysed
572 with Image J software version 1.43U (NIH). Stomata were counted within a 0.3-mm² area
573 near the middle of the leaf. Where possible, two measurements were recorded per leaf.
574 Stomatal density was calculated as the number of stomata per mm². Stomatal index was
575 calculated as follows: $S.I = [(number\ of\ stomata) / (number\ of\ other\ epidermal\ cells +$
576 $number\ of\ stomata)] * 100$. A minimum of 5 leaves were analysed per genotype.

577

578 **Bioluminescence Imaging**

579 Epidermal peels were incubated in 10/50 buffer containing 5 mM luciferin (D-luciferin
580 potassium salt, Melford) at 22°C for 2 h in the dark. A black 96-well cell culture plate was
581 loaded with 350 µl of 10/50 buffer and 5 mM luciferin per well and the chemical treatments
582 were randomly distributed along the plate. Peels were transferred so that each peel
583 occupied one well and bioluminescence was measured with a Photek HRPCS intensified
584 CCD camera system (Photek Ltd, St Leonards on Sea, UK) equipped with Peltier
585 temperature control. Peels were imaged for 1 h at 22°C and then for another 4 h 45 min
586 either at 22°C or 35°C. A clear plastic cover was used to minimise evaporation. Images
587 were captured every 15 min, with 14-min integration time. Acquisition and image analysis
588 were performed with the IMAGE32 software (Photek).

589

590 **RNA extraction**

591 For characterisation of mutant lines, 30 10-day-old seedlings (approx. 100 mg of tissue),
592 were flash frozen in liquid nitrogen and homogenized with 3-mm tungsten carbide beads
593 using a TissueLyser II (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). RNA from ground samples was then
594 extracted using the Spectrum™ Plant Total RNA kit (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, Missouri).
595 Samples were treated with DNase I (Sigma-Aldrich) to remove residual DNA. For
596 analyses of *HSP* transcripts, RNA was extracted from isolated epidermises (to enrich
597 samples in guard cell transcripts) and leaf discs, both derived from fully-expanded rosette
598 leaves. Each epidermis sample consisted of 20 abaxial epidermal peels, with each peel
599 approximately corresponding to half the surface area of the leaf blade. Peels were kept
600 in 10/0 buffer during sample preparation and were then processed similarly to a stomatal
601 bioassay. Following treatment, peels were flash frozen in liquid nitrogen. Leaf controls

602 consisted of four 5-mm diameter leaf disks and were treated as described above. Frozen
603 samples were homogenised at 4°C with 400 µl glass beads (glass beads, acid-washed,
604 425–600 µm, Sigma-Aldrich) and 350 µl Buffer RULT (Qiagen) containing 1% (v/v) β-
605 mercaptoethanol using a TissueLyser II (Qiagen). Homogenization treatment comprised
606 5 cycles of 1 min homogenization at 30 Hz followed by 1 min rest on ice. RNA was
607 extracted using the RNeasy UCP Micro Kit (Qiagen).

608

609 **Transcript Abundance**

610 Isolated RNA was quantified using a NanoDrop spectrophotometer and reverse
611 transcribed using the High Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription kit (Applied Biosystems,
612 Foster City, California) according to the manufacturer's instructions. qPCR reactions were
613 performed with 2X Brilliant III SYBR Green QPCR (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara,
614 California). Data were collected and analysed using the MxPro software (Agilent
615 Technologies). Three biological and 3 technical repeats were performed for each sample
616 and relative transcript abundance calculated using the $2^{(-\Delta\Delta CT)}$ method (Livak *et al.*,
617 2001). Biological repeats refer to an independent experiment, using different tissue
618 samples. Primer sequences for RT-qPCR experiments are provided in Supplemental
619 Table 3.

620

621 **Statistical analyses**

622 SigmaPlot v13 (Systat Software Inc), IBM®-SPSS-Statistic®23 (IBM) and R (R
623 Development Core Team, 2013) were used to analyse quantitative data.

624

625 **Accession Numbers**

626 14-3-3 *CHI* (At4g09000), 14-3-3 *KAPPA* (At5g65430), 14-3-3 *LAMBDA* (At5g10450), 14-
627 3-3 *MU* (At2g42590), 14-3-3 *NU* (At3g02520), 14-3-3 *OMEGA* (At1g78300), 14-3-3
628 *OMICRON* (At1g34760), 14-3-3 *PHI* (At1g35160), 14-3-3 *PI* (At1g78220), 14-3-3 *PSI*
629 (At5g38480), 14-3-3 *RHO/IOTA* (At1g26480), 14-3-3 *UPSILON* (At5g16050), *AHA1*
630 (At2g18960), *AHA2* (At4g30190), *AHA5* (At2g24520), *ARP6* (AT3G33520), *BLUS1*
631 (At4g14480), *CNGC6* (At2g23980), *FT* (At1g65480), *GC1* (At1g22690), *HSP18.2*
632 (AT5G59720), *HSP70* (At3g12580), *MYB60* (At1g08810), *OSCA1* (At4g04340),
633 *PATROL1* (At5g06970), *PHOT1* (AT3G45780), *PHOT2* (At5g58140), *PIF4* (At2g43010),
634 *PP2AA3* (At1g13320), *PPI1* (At4g27500), *PPI2* (At3g15340), *TPC1* (At4g03560).

635

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643

644 **Figure Legends**

645 **Figure 1.** Isolated Arabidopsis guard cells sense elevations in temperature.

646 **(A)** High temperature induces stomatal opening in isolated epidermal tissue.
647 Representative image of guard cells treated at 22°C and 35°C. Scale bar length = 5 µm.

648 **(B)** Guard cells respond to a range of temperatures in white light and dark conditions.
649 Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated epidermises from fully expanded rosette
650 leaves. Peels were incubated at 22°C for 2 h followed by incubation at 22°C, 30°C, 35°C,
651 or 40°C for a further 2 h. WL: White light. Bars = \pm SE. * indicates significant differences
652 by Tukey's post-hoc at $p < 0.05$ (n=86–90, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from
653 different plants). P values from a two-way ANOVA analysis comparing stomatal aperture,
654 with temperature and light as factors, are shown below graphs to highlight whether a
655 significant interaction between light and response to temperature exists. **(C)** Changes in
656 stomatal aperture in response to high temperature are statistically significant within 45
657 min ($p < 0.01$). Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated epidermises maintained
658 in white light. Peels were incubated at 22°C for 2 h before transfer to 35°C. Bars = \pm SE
659 (n=60–90, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different plants). n.s. = not
660 significant.

661

662 **Figure 2.** High temperature-induced stomatal opening in isolated guard cells requires
663 phototropin, but not components of high-temperature signalling pathways.

664 **(A-C)** Loss of function mutants of genes involved in high-temperature signalling have no
665 impairment in stomatal opening at 35°C. **(D)** Phototropins are required for stomatal
666 opening in response to high temperature. Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated
667 epidermises from fully expanded rosette leaves, exposed to white light. Peels were
668 incubated at 22°C for 2 h followed by incubation at 22°C or 35°C for a further 2 h. Col-0
669 controls were carried out in parallel. Bars = \pm SE. * indicates significant differences by
670 Tukey's post-hoc at $p < 0.05$ (n=90, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different

671 plants). P values from a two-way ANOVA analysis comparing stomatal apertures, with
672 genotype and temperature as factors, are shown below graphs to highlight whether a
673 significant interaction between genotype and response to temperature exists. n.s. = not
674 significant.

675

676 **Figure 3.** High temperature-induced stomatal opening in isolated guard cells requires
677 plasma membrane H⁺-ATPase activity.

678 **(A)** Treatment with the plasma membrane (PM) H⁺-ATPase inhibitor vanadate reduces
679 high temperature-induced stomatal opening in Arabidopsis (Col-0). **(B)** Mutants deficient
680 in the PM H⁺-ATPases AHA1 and AHA2 display reduced stomatal opening at high
681 temperature. **(C)** PATROL1 is essential for stomatal opening. The PM H⁺-ATPase-
682 interacting PPI1 and PPI2 proteins are not required for high temperature-mediated
683 stomatal opening. Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated epidermises from fully
684 expanded rosette leaves, exposed to white light. Peels were incubated at 22°C for 2 h,
685 followed by incubation at 22°C or 35°C for a further 2 h. For mutant analysis Col-0 controls
686 were carried out in parallel. Bars = ± SE, * indicates significant differences by Tukey's
687 post-hoc at p < 0.05 (n=90, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different plants).
688 P values from a two-way ANOVA analysis comparing stomatal apertures, with
689 temperature and vanadate treatment (A) or genotype (B) as factors, are shown below
690 graphs to highlight whether a significant interaction between each factor and response to
691 temperature exists. n.s. = not significant.

692

693 **Figure 4.** Multiple members of the 14-3-3 family contribute to high temperature-induced
694 stomatal opening.

695 **(A)** High temperature-induced stomatal opening in epsilon group mutants. **(B)** High
696 temperature-induced stomatal opening in non-epsilon group mutants. **(C)** Disrupting the
697 interaction of 14-3-3 proteins with their client proteins inhibits high temperature-induced
698 stomatal opening in Arabidopsis (Col-0). **(D)** 14-3-3 proteins are not functionally
699 redundant as quadruple 14-3-3 mutants do not display additive impairment in high
700 temperature-induced stomatal opening (*k: kappa, l: lambda, p: phi, c: chi, u: upsilon, n:*
701 *nu*). Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated epidermises from fully expanded
702 rosette leaves, exposed to white light. Peels were incubated at 22°C for 2 h followed by
703 incubation at 22°C or 35°C for a further 2 h. For mutant analysis Col-0 controls were
704 carried out in parallel. Bars = ± SE. *indicates significant differences by Tukey's post-hoc
705 at $p < 0.05$ ($n=90$, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different plants). P values
706 from a two-way ANOVA analysis comparing stomatal apertures, with temperature and
707 genotype (A, B, D) or AICAR treatment (C) as factors, are shown below graphs to highlight
708 whether a significant interaction between each factor and response to temperature exists.
709 n.s. = not significant.

710

711 **Figure 5.** High temperature-mediated stomatal opening in isolated guard cells is not
712 mediated by import of extracellular calcium.

713 **(A)** Larger stomatal apertures are observed at 35°C in the presence and absence of
714 calcium chloride. Extracellular calcium dose response curves at 22°C and 35°C.
715 Experiment performed in Col-0. The concentration of calcium with no added CaCl₂ was

716 estimated to be approximately 35 μM . **(B)** Incubation with the calcium chelator BAPTA
717 leads to increased stomatal apertures in response to high temperature. Experiment
718 performed in Col-0. **(C)** Incubation with the divalent calcium chelator EGTA leads to
719 increased stomatal apertures in response to high temperature. **(D)** The effect of calcium
720 on high temperature-induced stomatal opening is not mediated by verapamil-sensitive
721 calcium channels. **(E)** The calcium channels TPC1 and OSCA1 are not required for high
722 temperature-induced stomatal opening. **(F)** Treatment with the intracellular calcium
723 chelator BAPTA-AM impairs stomatal opening in response to high temperature. Carrier:
724 0.1% (v/v) DMSO + 0.025% (v/v) Pluronic F-127. Stomatal bioassays were performed on
725 isolated epidermises from fully expanded rosette leaves, exposed to white light. Peels
726 were incubated at 22°C for 2 h followed by incubation at 22°C or 35°C for a further 2 h.
727 For mutant analysis Col-0 controls were carried out in parallel. Bars = \pm SE. * indicates
728 significant differences by Tukey's post-hoc at $p < 0.05$ (n=90, measured from 3 separate
729 leaves, all from different plants). P values from a two-way ANOVA analysis comparing
730 stomatal apertures, with temperature and pharmacological treatment (B, C, D, F) or
731 genotype (E) treatment as factors, are shown below graphs to highlight whether a
732 significant interaction between each factor and response to temperature exists. n.s. = not
733 significant.

734

735 **Figure 6.** Phototropins promote leaf cooling and rosette conductance at 22°C.

736 **(A)** Dynamics of rosette temperature in Col-0, *aha2-5*, and *phot1/phot2* plants maintained
737 at a photon irradiance of $150 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and a constant temperature of 22°C with a
738 VPD_{air} of 0.93 kPa. Bars = \pm SE (n=7) **(B)** Thermal images of plants shown in (A) at 5 h

739 following light onset. Scale bar represents 2 cm on all images. **(C)** Dynamics of rosette
740 conductance ($E/VPD_{\text{leaf-air}}$) in plants grown as in (A). This was calculated from gravimetric
741 whole-plant transpiration (E) measurements and $VPD_{\text{leaf-air}}$. Bars = \pm SE (n=7). **(D)**
742 Average $E/VPD_{\text{leaf-air}}$ at 8.5 h after light onset. Bars = \pm SE (n=7). Statistical analyses were
743 performed by one-way ANOVA with Tukey post-hoc analysis, and different letters indicate
744 significant differences at $p < 0.01$.

745
746 **Figure 7.** Phototropins promote leaf cooling and rosette conductance at high
747 temperature.

748 **(A)** Dynamics of rosette temperature in Col-0, *aha2-5*, and *phot1/phot2* plants maintained
749 at a photon irradiance of $150 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and a constant temperature of 22°C with a
750 VPD_{air} of 0.93 kPa (left) and transferred at 3 h to 33°C with a $VPD_{\text{air}} = 1.2$ kPa (right). Bars
751 = \pm SE (n=7) **(B)** Thermal images of plants shown in (A) at 5 h following light onset and 2
752 h after transfer to high temperature. Scale bar represents 2 cm on all images. **(C)**
753 Dynamics of rosette conductance ($E/VPD_{\text{leaf-air}}$) in plants grown as in (A). This was
754 calculated from gravimetric whole-plant transpiration (E) measurements and $VPD_{\text{leaf-air}}$.
755 Bars = \pm SE (n=7). **(D)** Average $E/VPD_{\text{leaf-air}}$ 8.5 h after light onset. Bars = \pm SE (n=7).
756 Statistical analyses were performed by one-way ANOVA with Tukey post-hoc analysis,
757 and different letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.01$.

758
759 **Figure 8.** Transcriptional induction of high temperature-regulated genes in guard cells is
760 not inhibited by pharmacologically impairing 14-3-3–plasma membrane H^+ -ATPase
761 interaction. **(A)** Transcript abundance of *HSP70* and *HSP18.2* following AICAR and

762 temperature treatments. Epidermal peels from fully expanded rosette leaves were
763 incubated at 22°C for 2 h before incubation at 22°C or 35°C for 2 h. *TIP41* was used as a
764 control gene. Bars = \pm SD (n=3). **(B)** *HSP70::LUC* bioluminescence in detached leaf
765 epidermises following AICAR and temperature treatments. Arrow denotes temperature
766 shift. An equimolar amount of mannitol was used as an additional osmotic control. Bars =
767 \pm SD (n=12).

768

769 **Figure 9.** Possible sites of high temperature signal integration during stomatal opening in
770 white light. Stomatal opening in isolated guard cells following dark to blue light transfer
771 involves phototropin-mediated phosphorylation of BLUS1 which then activates plasma
772 membrane (PM) H⁺-ATPases. PATROL1 is required for AHA1 insertion into the PM. In
773 prolonged white light, we observed a prominent role for phototropins and redundant
774 interactions between H⁺-ATPases and 14-3-3 proteins in promoting stomatal opening. A
775 partial role for BLUS1 was observed, suggesting the existence of a phototropin-mediated,
776 BLUS1-independent pathway in these conditions. Complete stomatal opening in isolated
777 guard cells at high temperature requires phototropins, PM H⁺-ATPase activity and
778 redundant activities of 14-3-3 proteins. A partial role for BLUS1 was identified. A
779 requirement for phototropins in elevating stomatal conductance at high temperature was
780 additionally observed in whole leaves. Some phototropin-independent increases in
781 stomatal opening and rosette conductance at high temperature were also observed. High
782 temperature may stimulate phototropin activity directly, phototropin signalling or H⁺-
783 ATPase activity. Increased H⁺-ATPase activity may result from enhanced 14-3-3 binding.

784

785 **Supplemental Figure legends**

786

787

788 **Supplemental Figure S1.** Barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) and *Commelina communis* guard cells
789 sense temperature in the light and the dark

790 **Supplemental Figure S2.** Stomata remain viable after treatment at 35°C

791

792 **Supplemental Figure S3.** *ft* mutants display impaired stomatal opening responses when
793 transferred from dark to light.

794

795 **Supplemental Figure S4.** High temperature-induced stomatal opening in isolated guard
796 cells requires plasma membrane H⁺-ATPase activity (additional mutant alleles for *AHA1*
797 and *AHA2*).

798 **Supplemental Figure S5.** Morphology of Col-0, *aha2-5*, and *phot1/phot2* mutants under
799 experimental treatments.

800 **Supplemental Figure S6.** *aha-5* and *phot1/phot2* mutants do not display altered stomatal
801 density or index.

802

803 **Supplemental Figure S7.** Transcriptional induction of high temperature-regulated genes
804 is not inhibited by pharmacologically impairing 14-3-3–plasma membrane H⁺-ATPase
805 interaction.

806

807 **Supplemental Table S1.** Mutant lines.

808 **Supplemental Table S2A.** Primers used for genotyping – T-DNA spanning.

809 **Supplemental Table S2B.** Primers used for genotyping – T-DNA-specific.

810 **Supplemental Table S3.** Primers used for RT-qPCR.

811

812

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Figure 1. Isolated Arabidopsis guard cells sense elevations in temperature.

(A) High temperature induces stomatal opening in isolated epidermal tissue. Representative image of guard cells treated at 22°C and 35°C. Scale bar length = 5 μm. **(B)** Guard cells respond to a range of temperatures in white light and dark conditions. Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated epidermises from fully expanded rosette leaves. Peels were incubated at 22°C for 2 h followed by incubation at 22°C, 30°C, 35°C, or 40°C for a further 2 h. WL: White light. Bars = ± SE. * indicates significant differences by Tukey's post-hoc at p < 0.05 (n=86–90, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different plants). P values from a two-way ANOVA analysis comparing stomatal aperture, with temperature and light as factors, are shown below graphs to highlight whether a significant interaction between light and response to temperature exists. **(C)** Changes in stomatal aperture in response to high temperature are statistically significant within 45 min (p < 0.01). Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated epidermises maintained in white light. Peels were incubated at 22°C for 2 h before transfer to 35°C. Bars = ± SE (n=60–90, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different plants). n.s. = not significant.

Figure 2. High temperature-induced stomatal opening in isolated guard cells requires phototropin, but not components of high-temperature signalling pathways.

(A-C) Loss of function mutants of genes involved in high-temperature signalling have no impairment in stomatal opening at 35°C. **(D)** Phototropins are required for stomatal opening in response to high temperature. Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated epidermises from fully expanded rosette leaves, exposed to white light. Peels were incubated at 22°C for 2 h followed by incubation at 22°C or 35°C for a further 2 h. Col-0 controls were carried out in parallel. Bars = \pm SE. * indicates significant differences by Tukey's post-hoc at $p < 0.05$ ($n=90$, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different plants). P values from a two-way ANOVA analysis comparing stomatal apertures, with genotype and temperature as factors, are shown below graphs to highlight whether a significant interaction between genotype and response to temperature exists. n.s. = not significant.

Figure 3. High temperature-induced stomatal opening in isolated guard cells requires plasma membrane H⁺-ATPase activity.

(A) Treatment with the plasma membrane (PM) H⁺-ATPase inhibitor vanadate reduces high temperature-induced stomatal opening in Arabidopsis (*Col-0*). **(B)** Mutants deficient in the PM H⁺-ATPases AHA1 and AHA2 display reduced stomatal opening at high temperature. **(C)** PATROL1 is essential for stomatal opening. The PM H⁺-ATPase-interacting PPI1 and PPI2 proteins are not required for high temperature-mediated stomatal opening. Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated epidermises from fully expanded rosette leaves, exposed to white light. Peels were incubated at 22°C for 2 h, followed by incubation at 22°C or 35°C for a further 2 h. For mutant analysis *Col-0* controls were carried out in parallel. Bars = \pm SE, * indicates significant differences by Tukey's post-hoc at $p < 0.05$ ($n=90$, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different plants). P values from a two-way ANOVA analysis comparing stomatal apertures, with temperature and vanadate treatment (A) or genotype (B) as factors, are shown below graphs to highlight whether a significant interaction between each factor and response to temperature exists. n.s. = not significant.

Figure 4.

Figure 4. Multiple members of the 14-3-3 family contribute to high temperature-induced stomatal opening.

(A) High temperature-induced stomatal opening in epsilon group mutants. **(B)** High temperature-induced stomatal opening in non-epsilon group mutants. **(C)** Disrupting the interaction of 14-3-3 proteins with their client proteins inhibits high temperature-induced stomatal opening in Arabidopsis (Col-0). **(D)** 14-3-3 proteins are not functionally redundant as quadruple 14-3-3 mutants do not display additive impairment in high temperature-induced stomatal opening (*k. kappa, l. lambda, p. phi, c. chi, u. upsilon, n. nu*). Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated epidermises from fully expanded rosette leaves, exposed to white light. Peels were incubated at 22°C for 2 h followed by incubation at 22°C or 35°C for a further 2 h. For mutant analysis Col-0 controls were carried out in parallel. Bars = \pm SE. *indicates significant differences by Tukey's post-hoc at $p < 0.05$ (n=90, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different plants). P values from a two-way ANOVA analysis comparing stomatal apertures, with temperature and genotype (A, B, D) or AICAR treatment (C) as factors, are shown below graphs to highlight whether a significant interaction between each factor and response to temperature exists. n.s. = not significant.

Figure 5.

Figure 5. High temperature-mediated stomatal opening in isolated guard cells is not mediated by import of extracellular calcium.

(A) Larger stomatal apertures are observed at 35°C in the presence and absence of calcium chloride. Extracellular calcium dose response curves at 22°C and 35°C. Experiment performed in Col-0. The concentration of calcium with no added CaCl₂ was estimated to be approximately 35 μM. **(B)** Incubation with the calcium chelator BAPTA leads to increased stomatal apertures in response to high temperature. Experiment performed in Col-0. **(C)** Incubation with the divalent calcium chelator EGTA leads to increased stomatal apertures in response to high temperature. **(D)** The effect of calcium on high temperature-induced stomatal opening is not mediated by verapamil-sensitive calcium channels. **(E)** The calcium channels TPC1 and OSCA1 are not required for high temperature-induced stomatal opening. **(F)** Treatment with the intracellular calcium chelator BAPTA-AM impairs stomatal opening in response to high temperature. Carrier: 0.1% (v/v) DMSO + 0.025% (v/v) Pluronic F-127. Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated epidermises from fully expanded rosette leaves, exposed to white light. Peels were incubated at 22°C for 2 h followed by incubation at 22°C or 35°C for a further 2 h. For mutant analysis Col-0 controls were carried out in parallel. Bars = ± SE. * indicates significant differences by Tukey's post-hoc at p < 0.05 (n=90, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different plants). P values from a two-way ANOVA analysis comparing stomatal apertures, with temperature and pharmacological treatment (B, C, D, F) or genotype (E) treatment as factors, are shown below graphs to highlight whether a significant interaction between each factor and response to temperature exists. n.s. = not significant.

Figure 6. Phototropins promote leaf cooling and rosette conductance at 22°C .

(A) Dynamics of rosette temperature in Col-0, *aha2-5*, and *phot1/phot2* plants maintained at a photon irradiance of $150 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and a constant temperature of 22°C with a VPD_{air} of 0.93 kPa. Bars = \pm SE (n=7) **(B)** Thermal images of plants shown in (A) at 5 h following light onset. Scale bar represents 2 cm on all images. **(C)** Dynamics of rosette conductance ($E/\text{VPD}_{\text{leaf-air}}$) in plants grown as in (A). This was calculated from gravimetric whole-plant transpiration (E) measurements and $\text{VPD}_{\text{leaf-air}}$. Bars = \pm SE (n=7). **(D)** Average $E/\text{VPD}_{\text{leaf-air}}$ at 8.5 h after light onset. Bars= \pm SE (n=7). Statistical analyses were performed by one-way ANOVA with Tukey post-hoc analysis, and different letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.01$.

Figure 7. Phototropins promote leaf cooling and rosette conductance at high temperature.

(A) Dynamics of rosette temperature in Col-0, *aha2-5*, and *phot1/phot2* plants maintained at a photon irradiance of $150 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and a constant temperature of 22°C with a VPD_{air} of 0.93 kPa (left) and transferred at 3 h to 33°C with a $\text{VPD}_{\text{air}} = 1.2 \text{ kPa}$ (right). Bars = $\pm \text{SE}$ ($n=7$)

(B) Thermal images of plants shown in (A) at 5 h following light onset and 2 h after transfer to high temperature. Scale bar represents 2 cm on all images. **(C)** Dynamics of rosette conductance ($\text{E}/\text{VPD}_{\text{leaf-air}}$) in plants grown as in (A). This was calculated from gravimetric whole-plant transpiration (E) measurements and $\text{VPD}_{\text{leaf-air}}$. Bars = $\pm \text{SE}$ ($n=7$). **(D)** Average $\text{E}/\text{VPD}_{\text{leaf-air}}$ 8.5 h after light onset. Bars = $\pm \text{SE}$ ($n=7$). Statistical analyses were performed by one-way ANOVA with Tukey post-hoc analysis, and different letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.01$.

Figure 8. Transcriptional induction of high temperature-regulated genes in guard cells is not inhibited by pharmacologically impairing 14-3-3–plasma membrane H⁺-ATPase interaction.

(A) Transcript abundance of *HSP70* and *HSP18.2* following AICAR and temperature treatments. Epidermal peels from fully expanded rosette leaves were incubated at 22°C for 2 h before incubation at 22°C or 35°C for 2 h. *TIP41* was used as a control gene. Bars = \pm SD (n=3). **(B)** *HSP70::LUC* bioluminescence in detached leaf epidermises following AICAR and temperature treatments. Arrow denotes temperature shift. An equimolar amount of mannitol was used as an additional osmotic control. Bars = \pm SD (n=12).

Figure 9. Possible sites of high temperature signal integration during stomatal opening in white light.

Stomatal opening in isolated guard cells following dark to blue light transfer involves phototropin-mediated phosphorylation of BLUS1 which then activates plasma membrane (PM) H⁺-ATPases. PATROL1 is required for AHA1 insertion into the PM. In prolonged white light, we observed a prominent role for phototropins and redundant interactions between H⁺-ATPases and 14-3-3 proteins in promoting stomatal opening. A partial role for BLUS1 was observed, suggesting the existence of a phototropin-mediated, BLUS1-independent pathway in these conditions. Complete stomatal opening in isolated guard cells at high temperature requires phototropins, PM H⁺-ATPase activity and redundant activities of 14-3-3 proteins. A partial role for BLUS1 was identified. A requirement for phototropins in elevating stomatal conductance at high temperature was additionally observed in whole leaves. Some phototropin-independent increases in stomatal opening and rosette conductance at high temperature were also observed. High temperature may stimulate phototropin activity directly, phototropin signalling or H⁺-ATPase activity. Increased H⁺-ATPase activity may result from enhanced 14-3-3 binding.

Supplemental Figure S1. Barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) and *Commelina communis* guard cells sense temperature in the light and the dark. Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated epidermises. Peels were incubated at 22° C for 2 h followed by incubation at 22° C or 40° C for a further 2 h. WL: White light. Bars = \pm SE. * indicates significant differences by Tukey's post-hoc at $p < 0.05$ (Barley $n=90$, *Commelina communis* $n=30$; measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different plants). P values from a two-way ANOVA analysis comparing stomatal aperture, with temperature and light as factors, are shown below graphs to highlight whether a significant interaction between light environment and response to temperature exists. n.s. = not significant.

Supplemental Figure S2. Stomata remain viable after treatment at 35° C. **(A) - (C)** Isolated epidermis from a fully expanded *Arabidopsis* (Col-0) rosette leaf incubated at 22° C for 4 h. (A) Bright field, (B) Fluorescein diacetate staining, (C) Overlay. Scale bar length = 100 μm. **(D) - (F)** Isolated epidermis incubated at 22° C for 2 h followed by incubation at 35° C for 2 h. (D) Bright field, (E) Fluorescein diacetate staining, (F) Overlay. Scale bar length = 100 μm. **(G)** Percentage of viable guard cells under the experimental conditions. WL: white light. **(H)** High temperature-induced stomatal opening is reversible. Guard cells incubated at 35° C for 2 h retain their ability to close when transferred to a lower temperature (22° C) for 2 h (all measurements performed following 2 h of treatment). WL: White light. Bars = \pm SE * indicates significant differences by Tukey's post-hoc at $p < 0.05$ ($n=80-90$, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different plants). P values from a two-way ANOVA analysis comparing stomatal aperture, with temperature and light as factors, are shown below graphs to highlight whether a significant interaction between light and response to temperature exists. n.s. = not significant.

Supplemental Figure S3. *ft* mutants display impaired stomatal opening responses when transferred from dark to light. Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated epidermises from fully expanded rosette leaves maintained in the dark, transferred to a mixture of blue ($10 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and red ($50 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) light for 3 h or treated with $10 \mu\text{M}$ fusicoccin (FC) in the dark for 3 h. All experiments were performed at 22°C . Bars = \pm SE ($n = 135$, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different plants). * indicates significant differences by Tukey's post-hoc at $p < 0.05$.

Supplemental Figure S4. High temperature-induced stomatal opening in isolated guard cells requires plasma membrane H⁺-ATPase activity (additional mutant alleles for *AHA1* and *AHA2*). Stomatal bioassays were performed on isolated epidermises from fully expanded rosette leaves that were exposed to white light. Peels were incubated at 22° C for 2 h followed by incubation at 22° C or 35° C for a further 2 h. Bars = ± SE. * indicates significant differences by Tukey's post-hoc at $p < 0.05$ (n=90, measured from 3 separate leaves, all from different plants). P values from a two-way ANOVA analysis comparing stomatal apertures, with genotype and temperature as factors, are shown below graphs to highlight whether a significant interaction between genotype and response to temperature exists.

Supplemental Figure S5. Morphology of Col-0, *aha2-5*, and *phot1/phot2* mutants under experimental treatments. Seedlings were maintained at a photon irradiance of $150 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and a constant temperature of 22°C with a VPD_{air} of 0.93 kPa during experiments analysing leaf temperature and rosette conductance (Figures 6 and 7). Photographs were taken every two days from 15 to 33 days after sowing (DAS) and are shown together with projected rosette areas. Scale bar represents 4 cm on all images.

A

Supplemental Figure S6. *aha-5* and *phot1/phot2* mutants do not display altered stomatal density or index. Stomatal density (**A**) and stomatal index (**B**) in Col-0, *aha2-5*, and *phot1/phot2* mutants maintained at a photon irradiance of 150 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and a constant temperature of 22° C with a VPD_{air} of 0.93 kPa. Measurements were taken from the abaxial surface of fully expanded rosette leaves at 5 weeks. Bars = \pm SE. No significant differences were detected between genotypes with a one-way ANOVA analysis.

Supplemental Figure S7. Transcriptional induction of high temperature-regulated genes is not inhibited by pharmacologically impairing 14-3-3–plasma membrane H⁺-ATPase interaction. (A) Tissue-specific enrichment of *GC1* and *MYB60* transcripts between leaf and isolated epidermal tissue. *TIP41* and *PP2AA3* were used as control genes. (B) Changes in transcript abundance of *HSP70* and *HSP18.2* at 35° C in isolated epidermal peels. *PP2AA3* was used as a control gene. (C) Changes in transcript abundance of *HSP70* and *HSP18.2* at 35° C in leaf tissue. *TIP41* was used as a control gene. (D) Changes in transcript abundance of *HSP70* and *HSP18.2* at 35° C in leaf tissue. *PP2AA3* was used as a control gene. Samples were incubated at 22° C for 2 h followed by incubation at either 22° C or 35° C for a further 2 h. Bars = ± SD (n=3).

Supplemental Table S1. Mutant lines

Name	Gene ID	Line	Previously characterised by	Insertion point	Nature of mutation
<i>14-3-3 chi</i>	At4g09000	SALK_018664	(Van Kleeff et al., 2014)	Exon 1	Null
<i>14-3-3 kappa</i>	At5g65430	SALK_148929	(Yang et al., 2009; Van Kleeff et al., 2014)	Intron 1	Null
<i>14-3-3 lambda</i>	At5g10450	SALK_129554	(Yang et al., 2009; Van Kleeff et al., 2014)	Intron 2	Null
<i>14-3-3 mu</i>	At2g42590	SALK_004455	(Cao et al., 2007; Mayfield et al., 2007)	Promoter	Knocked down
<i>14-3-3 nu</i>	At3g02520	SALK_084141	N/A	Exon 3	Knocked down
<i>14-3-3 omega</i>	At1g78300	SAIL_904_D03	N/A	3'-UTR	Knocked down
<i>14-3-3 omicron</i>	At1g34760	SALK_123168	(Yang et al., 2013)	Promoter	Null
<i>14-3-3 phi</i>	At1g35160	SALK_088321	(Van Kleeff et al., 2014)	Exon 3	Null
<i>14-3-3 pi</i>	At1g78220	SALK_053026	N/A	Promoter	
<i>14-3-3 psi</i>	At5g38480	SALK_012032	N/A	Promoter	Knocked down
<i>14-3-3 rho/iota</i>	At1g26480	SALK_110798	N/A	Intron 2	
<i>14-3-3 epsilon</i>	At5g16050	SALK_080414	(Van Kleeff et al., 2014)	5'-UTR	Null
<i>14-3-3 kappa/lambda/phi/chi</i>	At5g65430/At5g10450/At1g35160/At4g09000	SALK_148929/SALK_129554/SALK_088321/SALK_018664	(Van Kleeff et al., 2014)	Intron 1/Intron 2/Exon 3/Exon 1	Null
<i>14-3-3 kappa/lambda/epsilon/nu</i>	At5g65430/At5g10450/At3g02520	SALK_148929/SALK_129554/SALK_080414/SALK_114711	(Van Kleeff et al., 2014)	Intron 1/Intron 2/5'-UTR/Exon 1	Null
<i>14-3-3 epsilon/nu/phi/chi</i>	At5g16050/At3g02520/At1g35160/At4g09000	SALK_080414/SALK_114711/SALK_088321/SALK_018664	(Van Kleeff et al., 2014)	5'-UTR/Exon 1/Exon 3/Exon 1	Null
<i>aha1-6</i>	At2g18960	SALK_016325	(Haruta et al., 2010)	Intron 1	Knocked down
<i>aha1-8</i>	At2g18960	SALK_118350	(Santi and Schmidt, 2009; Haruta et al., 2010)	Intron 8	Knocked down
<i>aha2-4</i>	At4g30190	SALK_082786	(Santi and Schmidt, 2009; Haruta et al., 2010)	Intron 4	Null
<i>aha2-5</i>	At4g30190	SALK_022010	(Haruta et al., 2010)	Intron 3	Knocked down
<i>aha5</i>	At2g24520	SALK_127844	(Hayashi et al., 2014)	Exon 4	Null
<i>arp6-1</i>	AT3G33520	GARLIC_599_G03	(Deal et al., 2005)	Exon 1	Null
<i>blus1-3</i>	At4g14480	SALK_000221	(Takemiya et al., 2013)	5'-UTR	Null
<i>cngc6</i>	At2g23980	SALK_042207	(Gao et al., 2012)	Intron 2	Knocked down
<i>ft-10</i>	At1G65480	GABI-Kat_290E08	(Yoo et al. 2005)	Intron 1	Knocked down
<i>ft-773</i>	At1G65480	SAIL_773_F04	N/A	Intron 3	Null
<i>HSP70::LUC</i>	N/A	N/A	(Kumar and Wigge, 2010)	N/A	N/A
<i>osca1-4</i>	At4g04340	SALK_038633	N/A	5'UTR	
<i>patrol1-2</i>	At5g06970	SALK_018676	(Zhu et al., 2018)	Intron 2	Null
<i>phot1-5</i>	At3G45780	N/A	(Huala et al., 1997)	Intron 8	Null
<i>phot2-1</i>	At5G58140	N/A	(Kagawa et al., 2001)	Intron 11	Null
<i>phot1-5/2-1</i>	At3G45780/At5G58140	NA	(Kinoshita et al., 2001)	Intron 8/Intron 11	Null
<i>pif4-101</i>	At2G43010	Garlic_114_G06	(Lorrain et al., 2008)	Exon 5	Null
<i>ppi1-2</i>	At4g27500	SALK_009375	(Anzi et al., 2008)	5'-UTR	Null
<i>ppi2-3</i>	At3g15340	SALK_150915	N/A	Exon 4	
<i>tpc1-2</i>	AT4G03560	SALK_145413	(Peiter et al., 2005)	Exon 17	Null

Supplemental Table S2A. Primers used for genotyping – T-DNA spanning

Name	Gene ID	Forward primer 5' -> 3'	Reverse primer 5' -> 3'
14-3-3 <i>CHI</i>	At4g09000	CCCACGCGCAAATGAGTTAATC	AGATCCAAACCTGCTTAGCGAG
14-3-3 <i>EPSILON</i>	At1g22300	AGCCTACCGACAACGACTAATG	TCCAGATCAAGTAACAGCCCAG
14-3-3 <i>KAPPA</i>	At5g65430	GATCTGTTCTGGGATTCTCAGTT A	ATGTGTCCAGCTCAGCAATGGC TTCT
14-3-3 <i>LAMBDA</i>	At5g10450	TGTTTGCTCTGGAATCCTTAAGCT	GAGTGTCAAGCTCAGCTATGGCC TCC
14-3-3 <i>MU</i>	At2g42590	GACCCTTACTTGAGGCAAAGG	CGAAAGTGTACGCTCTTTTC
14-3-3 <i>NU</i>	At3g02520	TGGATTCTCACCTTGTTCCCAC	ACTAACAAGCAACGAAGCAGG
14-3-3 <i>OMEGA</i>	At1g78300	GATGAGGCGATTGCAGAGTTGG	AGTAATTGGCTTTACGCAGTCC
14-3-3 <i>OMICRON</i>	At1g34760	TGGCGGGAGAAACGAGACAG	TGCTCTCCTAGCACCAATCAC
14-3-3 <i>PHI</i>	At1g35160	AACGATGACCATGTGACCACG	TGCTGCTGCTTCTTTAATCTCC
14-3-3 <i>PI</i>	At1g78220	AAGGTGATGCTCTGTTCCCTCG	GTGAGTTAAGGGATGCTCGATG
14-3-3 <i>PSI</i>	At5g38480	CCGCTACGGGAATTTGAACCTG	TCAGCTTGTTCCGGCTAATTTCCG
14-3-3 <i>RHO/IOTA</i>	At1g26480	AACAAGCCGAGCGATACGAC	GGGTGAGGTTGTCTCTCAGG
14-3-3 <i>UPSILON</i>	At5g16050	CACGAGCTTGCTCCACATAG	TCAACAGTAAGTTCCTCGGTCTC
<i>AHA1-6</i>	At2g18960	TCCTTGCGATGGTTTCACGTTTG	GGAAGATGAAGAGTGCGGTTG
<i>AHA1-8</i>	At2g18960	ACTTGCGCTCTAACTACGTTGC	TTGGTTGTGAAAGCGGTCTG
<i>AHA2-4</i>	At4g30190	TGATGCTACAGATGCTGCTCG	AACGGGTGCTTCTTTGAGAAC
<i>AHA2-5</i>	At4g30190	CACTTCACCACCGCTATTTCC	TTTCGGCGTTGGATCGGATAC
<i>AHA5</i>	At2g24520	GGCGACTGGTTCTCATAGATTG	ACCATCTCCAGTCATGCCAC
<i>BLUS1</i>	At4g14480	GACCTTAATGCTGTGGGATTGG	GAATGGCATAACCACCCAGAG
<i>CNGC6</i>	At2g23980	ATGCATGGCGTGGGACAACC	CCACAAAGCCCCAACAATCTGC
<i>FT-773</i>	At1g65480	ATCAACTTCGAGAGTGCGATG	ATCATCACCGTTCGTTACTCG
<i>OSCA1-4</i>	At4g04340	GCGTGGCTTGCGTGTTACTTC	TCATACCCGAGCCAGTAAATCC
<i>PATROL1</i>	At5g06970	TGGAATGCTCGAACTCGCTG	TTAGCTCTGGCTACTGGATGG
<i>PPI1</i>	At4g27500	CAATGCCCGTGACCACTCTG	TTAGCCACAGGCCACTCTTC
<i>PPI2</i>	At3g15340	TTTGAGGAAGAAGATTGGGTGC	TCCATTGCTAACCAGGGCTTTC

Supplemental Table S2B. Primers used for genotyping – T-DNA detection

Name	Gene ID	Left border primer 5' -> 3'	Gene-specific primer 5' -> 3'
14-3-3 <i>CHI</i>	At4g09000	TGGTTCACGTAGTGGGCCATCG	AGATCCAAACCTGCTTAGCGAG
14-3-3 <i>EPSILON</i>	At1g22300	TAGCATCTGAATTTTCATAACCAATC TCGATACAC	AGCCTACCGACAACGACTAATG
14-3-3 <i>KAPPA</i>	At5g65430	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	ATGTGTCCAGCTCAGCAATGGC TTCT
14-3-3 <i>LAMBDA</i>	At5g10450	TGGTTCACGTAGTGGGCCATCG	GCTCGTTACAGGCGCTACTC
14-3-3 <i>MU</i>	At2g42590	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	CGAAAGTGTACGCTCTTTTC
14-3-3 <i>NU</i>	At3g02520	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	AATACTCAATCTTCTGGATTCT
14-3-3 <i>OMEGA</i>	At1g78300	TAGCATCTGAATTTTCATAACCAATC TCGATACAC	TCAATTCTCCTGATCGTGCCTG
14-3-3 <i>OMICRON</i>	At1g34760	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	TGCTCTCCTAGCACCAATCAC
14-3-3 <i>PHI</i>	At1g35160	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	TTGTTGGATCTCATTCTAGG
14-3-3 <i>PI</i>	At1g78220	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	ACGGACGATTTGCCTCAACG
14-3-3 <i>PSI</i>	At5g38480	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	TCAGCTTGTTTCGGCTAATTTTCG
14-3-3 <i>RHO/IOTA</i>	At1g26480	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	GGGTGAGGTTGTCTCTCAGG
14-3-3 <i>UPSILON</i>	At5g16050	TGGTTCACGTAGTGGGCCATCG	TCAACAGTAAGTTCCTCGGTCTC
<i>AHA1-6</i>	At2g18960	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	TTGGTTGTGAAAGCGGTCTG
<i>AHA1-8</i>	At2g18960	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	TCCTTGCATGGTTTCACGTTTG
<i>AHA2-4</i>	At4g30190	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	AACGGGTGCTTCTTTGAGAAC
<i>AHA2-5</i>	At4g30190	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	CACTTCACCACCGCTATTTCC
<i>AHA5</i>	At2g24520	TGGTTCACGTAGTGGGCCATCG	GCGACTGTTTCTCATAGATTG
<i>BLUS1</i>	At4g14480	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	GAATGGCATAACCACCCAGAG
<i>CNGC6</i>	At2g23980	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	ATGCATGGCGTGGGACAACC
<i>FT-773</i>	At1g65480	TAGCATCTGAATTTTCATAACCAATC TCGATACAC	ATCATCACCGTTCGTTACTCG
<i>OSCA1</i>	At4g04340	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	GCGTGGCTTGCCTGTTACTTC
<i>PATROL1</i>	At5g06970	TGGTTCACGTAGTGGGCCATCG	GCTGTGACTCTTGACGATGTTG
<i>PPI1</i>	At4g27500	ATTTTGCCGATTTTCGGAAC	CAGTAACCGCAATGCCCGTG
<i>PPI2</i>	At3g15340	TGGTTCACGTAGTGGGCCATCG	TCCATTGCTAACCGGGCTTTC

Supplemental Table S3. Primers used for qPCR

Name	Gene ID	Forward primer 5' -> 3'	Reverse primer 5' -> 3'
<i>14-3-3 MU</i>	AT2g42590	TGCTAAGCAGGCGTTTCGATG	CTCCACCAGCACCAGGTTTG
<i>14-3-3 OMEGA</i>	AT1g78300	GATGAGGCGATTGCAGAGTTGG	TCCTTGATCTCATCCGCAGC
<i>14-3-3 PI</i>	AT1g78220	GGTTGCCAAGCTGGAAGATATG	TTTGGTCGTTTCCTTTTCGAGTC
<i>14-3-3 PSI</i>	AT5g38480	TGCTGAGTTTAAGGCTGGTGC	GCTAACTCAGCAGTGGCAATG
<i>14-3-3 RHO</i>	AT1g26480	GGCCTTGCTCTTAACCTTCTCTG	GGGTGAGGTTGTCTCTCAGG
<i>ACT2</i>	AT3g18780	TCAGATGCCCAGAAGTGTGTTC	CCGTACAGATCCTTCCTGATATCC
<i>FT</i>	At1g65480	CCATTGGTTGGTGAAGTATATCC	TTGCCAAAGGTTGTTCCAGTT
<i>GC1</i>	AT1g22690	ACAGAGCCTGTGGAAGTTG	ATACTGGCGTAGCAAGGACA
<i>HSP18.2</i>	AT5g59720	AAGGCAACAATGGAGAATGG	GCACACAAGCTTTTTATTTGACA
<i>HSP70</i>	AT3g12580	GAAGTACAAGGCTGAGGATGAAGAAC	CTTCTCGTCCTTGATCGTGTTC
<i>MYB60</i>	AT1g08810	AGAACCGGACAAACAATTC	CCTTTGCTATGACCCTCTTC
<i>OSCA1</i>	AT4g04340	TGCTTGCTTGGGCAGTTCTTGTA	GGCAAGAACTGAAGCCTCATGT
<i>PP2AA3</i>	AT1g13320	TAACGTGGCCAAAATGATGC	GTTCTCCACAACCGCTTGGT
<i>PPI2</i>	AT3g15340	ACCAGAGCCTTCTGTTATGAG	AATCCGACCATCTTGGTTGAGC
<i>TIP41</i>	AT4g34270	GTGAAAAGTGTGGAGAGAAGCAA	TCAACTGGATACCCTTTTCGCA